

HEAVILY LOADED EXTREME LIGHTWEIGHT COMPONENTS MADE BY TAILORED FIBER PLACEMENT – COMPUTATIONAL DESIGN

ICCM23 – International Conference on Composite Materials

TV Lisbôa¹, L Bittrich¹, K Uhlig¹, and A. Spickenheuer¹

¹Leibniz-Institut für Polymerforschung Dresden e. V.

Summary

- » Substitution of a metallic heavy loaded part for a CFRP one
- » Equipment and part to be substituted
- » Flowchart of activities
- » Results
- » Application for presenting the concept of extreme lightweight structures (for kids and adults)

Equipment

Part to be substituted: C-Frame

- > Mass of the part (Steel): approx. 2.4 kg (around 30% of the equipment)
- > Displacement: 1.21 mm @ Force = 20 kN
- > Stiffness: 16.5 kN/mm
- > Specific stiffness: 6.9 kN/mm/kg

Flowchart of the development process

Topology Optimization

Optimization

Isotropic

Anisotropic

Design Adaptation

Adjusting/adapting the fiber orientations

Consideration of manufacturing boundary conditions & design aspects

Design Adaptation

Adjustment of the gripping position for testing

TFP-layout and Virtualization

Design and manufacturing of preforms

TFP-Layout and Virtualization

FE Model of the variable-axial TFP-structure

Finite Element Analyses

Consolidation of the part: fast low-cost prototyping

Silicone mold for the consolidation

Positive 3D-printed cast molds

Consolidation of the part: fast low-cost prototyping

VAP Infusion

Part and testing

Testing with DIC

Part and testing

FEM Analysis V1

$$IFF_1 = \frac{\sigma_2 + \sigma_3 + \sqrt{(\sigma_2 + \sigma_3)^2 + 4\tau_{23}^2}}{2R_{\perp}^t} \leq 1$$

FEM Analysis V2

One has added “**fillers**” to avoid out-of-plane undulation, reducing σ_3

Cross-fibers

FEM Analysis V2

Material	Mass	Stiffness	Specific Stiffness	Strength
Steel	2,4 kg	16,5 kN/mm	6,9 kN/mm/kg	~ 22 kN
TFP V1 (HT-CF / EP)	0,5 kg (-80 %)	~ 17 kN/mm	34 kN/mm/kg (+390 %)	~ 22 kN
TFP V2 (HT-CF / EP)	0,62 kg (-75 %)	~ 17 kN/mm	27 kN/mm/kg (+290 %)	~ 35 kN

Kontakt:

Dr. Tales de Vargas Lisbôa

Leibniz-Institut für Polymerforschung Dresden e. V.

Phone: +49 351 4658 1423

E-Mail: tales-lisboa@ipfdd.de

Web: www.ipfdd.de/tfp-technology

ZIM
Zentrales
Innovationsprogramm
Mittelstand

Gefördert durch:

Bundesministerium
für Wirtschaft
und Energie

aufgrund eines Beschlusses
des Deutschen Bundestages

The image shows the ZIM logo, which consists of a stylized 'Z' shape in red and yellow. To the right, there is text indicating funding by the German Federal Government, specifically the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy, based on a decision of the German Bundestag.

Thank you for your attention!

Questions?

